

Young Children's Androgynous Human Figure Drawings (Cephalopods): The Four Perspectives on Androgyny - Sociological, Psychological, Iconographic and Theological

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APA Citation: Chua, M. J. S., & Xie, G. H. (2022). Young children's androgynous human figure drawings (cephalopods): The four perspectives on androgyny - sociological, psychological, iconographic and theological. *Early Years Research*, 2(2), 23-30.

Abstract

One of the earliest schemata drawn by young children is the human figure. This human figure drawing remains most popular among the schemata used by counselors, therapists and psychologists in projective drawing tests, especially the Draw-a-Person (DAP) test. When a human figure first drawn by a young child, it appears very bizarre with no torso and/or limbs. If limbs are drawn, they are often attached to the head of the human figure. It has no clear features to distinguish its gender: male or female. The entire human figure drawing appears like a tadpole of some sort and it is often called a cephalopod or nicknamed 'tadpole man'. The young drawer might describe the cephalopod as 'daddy' at one moment and when asked again, might say it is 'mommy'. Hence, there is no consistency in the gender identification or discrimination in young children's human figure drawings. The authors of this short paper have decided to use term 'androgynous', i.e., indeterminate gender that can be partly male and partly female in appearance, to describe such drawings. In this short paper, the authors attempted to explore the androgynous cephalopod drawings done by young children and hypothesized that such drawings could be traced to the archetypal symbolism of Adam and Eve based on the biblical story of God's creation of man and woman.

Key Words: Adam, Androgyny, Cephalopod, Eve, Female, Human figure drawing, Male

Introduction

According to Cox (1993), among all the schemata drawn by children and adolescents as well as adults, the human figure drawing is most popular. As a result, most, if not all, of the projective drawing tests have often involved single human figure drawings (SHFDs), also commonly known as Draw-a-Person (DAP) test (alternatively also known as Draw-a-Man or Draw-a-Woman test), first popularized by Goodenough (1926). Maley (2009) claimed that young children draw "what they know rather than what they see" (Goodenough & Tyler, 1959, p. 316) long before they "can read and write – and understand the functions of reading and writing – they draw" (Maley, 2009, p. 3). This belief has been supported by several earlier studies such as Luquet (1913), and Piaget and Inhelder (1956, 1971) and later studies such as Crook (1985), Davis (1985), and Freeman and Cox (1985), mainly published toward

the end of the last century. In addition, young children also draw animals, flowers, houses, trees and shapes of all kinds.

Most children, if not all, as they approach three years of age, they exhibit "an increasing tendency to make circular strokes" (DiLeo, 1973, p. 4) in their kinesthetic drawings (e.g., circle, spiral, triangle). These kinesthetic drawings are gradually replaced with creating representational form of things (e.g., circle for face or body, triangle for dress) these young children know or remember than what they see (Eng, 1954; Spearing, 1912) - but Arnheim (1965, 1969) continued to insist that they draw what they see - as a way to the greater satisfaction. Most of these emerging representational drawings often constitute circles - the simplest pattern of all - what DiLeo (1973) described as "the universally selected pattern, and the most

common form in nature” (p. 4) and added that “[T]he child will continue to use it as he represents a variety of perceptions - head, eyes, mouth, trunk, ears, and even hair” (p. 4).

What do Young Children draw?

DiLeo (1973) has provided his answers to the question frequently asked by both parents and early childhood educators what young children draw: “(1) what is important to them: predominantly people, then animals, houses, trees; (2) some, but not all, of what is known about the object; (3) what is remembered at the time; (4) the idea colored by feelings; (5) what is seen, as in the sense used by Arnheim (1965, 1969); and (6) an inner, not an optical reality” (p. 10).

Based on his observation of innumerable drawings done by young children over the years, DiLeo (1973) came to his own conclusion that “children are expressionists for whom the object serves merely as a cue or catalyst. Whether drawing from a model or from memory, the result is the same” (p. 10).

In this short paper, the authors have chosen to focus on single human figure drawings (SHFDs) done by young children aged 3 to 5 years old.

Emergence of Cephalopod or Tadpole Man

Generally, children represent a single human figure drawing (SHFD) by what they deem is most essential. In fact, nothing is as interesting as a face to an infant or young child, and being fascinated by that circular configuration (i.e., the face) “wherein resides what eats, talks, sees, hears, smiles, and frowns” (DiLeo, 1973, p. 14) resembling an emoji¹ that the child would select that part of the anatomy as representing a human figure or person. Much later, young children add the appendages (i.e., limbs - arms and/or legs) to their circular human figures which look like the green Mike in the *Monsters, Inc.* Movie. This primitive circle representation of a human figure drawn by young children before the age of four has been termed cephalopod (see Figures 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d below) or tadpole man (including other terms *Kopffüssler* and *bonhomme têtard*), “all head and legs, so unreal and yet so unmistakably human - an uncanny reduction to essentials” (DiLeo, 1973, p. 14). Arnheim (1965) took issue with what he called the misnamed tadpoles being erroneously applied and misleading. He espoused his

view stating firmly that it was “the most striking case of misinterpretation due to realistic bias” (p. 188). He argued that the trunk of the so-called cephalopod is not left out but was included within the circle, and that consequently the arms and legs were correctly attached. It was only after the age of five that “children begin to draw a second circle to represent the body, the primacy of the head is proclaimed by its exaggerated size” (DiLeo, 1973, p. 14).

Figure 1a. A Cephalopod Drawing

Figure 1b. A Cephalopod Drawing

Figure 1c. A Cephalopod Drawing

Figure 1d. A Cephalopod Drawing

Which Gender in the Human Figure Drawings would be drawn first?

Another interesting question that is also often asked is whether young children draw a male or female human figure first. To answer this question, the authors have posed the same question to their friends and clients if they were to ask their young children to draw a single human figure. The response is not surprising to them at all: the boys will choose to draw a male human figure while the girls will choose to draw a female human figure. This is a genderized single human figure drawing or gSHFD for short: i.e., the boys draw a male figure; the girls, a female figure. However, the authors of this paper have also made an interesting observation that for younger children below four years of age, their SHFDs are often genderless or agender, which the authors have abbreviated it agSHRD. For instance, if a child is asked who the SHFD is, the young drawer might describe the human figure as ‘daddy’ at one moment and when asked again, might say it is ‘mommy’. Hence, there is no consistency in the gender

¹ Emojis are first invented by Shigetaka Kurita (b.1972), a Japanese interface designer, in the late nineties as a project for Docomo, the predominant mobile phone operator in Japan.

identification or discrimination in young children's SHFDs.

Sex-Gender Differences in Cephalopod Drawings

First of all, there is a need to differentiate between the two terms *sex* and *gender*. Although both terms appear to be very closely related, they are not totally the same. Moreover, it is also difficult to distinguish the exact meaning of the two terms. In other words, it is by no means the two terms *sex* and *gender* are the same although most people, if not all, use these two words interchangeably, assuming that they are synonymous. The term *sex* is generally determined by the anatomy of a person, either of two divisions, male and female. The other term *gender* refers a set of traits (masculine or feminine) that are seen and use to distinguish between male and female. To delve further into the concept of sex and gender, one may discover, for example, that a female by the anatomy of the physical body could have masculine traits such as preferring rough sports and body strength. While sex is biological, gender is a social construct defined by the society.

As mentioned earlier, cephalopod drawings are often agender or genderless (i.e., agSHRDs), and the gender of the cephalopod depends on what the young drawer has to say. Such cephalopod drawings can also be androgynous², sociologically or psychologically speaking. The common dictionary (e.g., Merriam-Webster) definition of androgyny or androgynous refers to the quality or state of being neither specifically feminine or masculine, but a combination of both feminine and masculine features.

However, from the sociological perspective, androgyny is seen as "sociologically problematic because it does not fit neatly into the binary of male and female, and what 'male' and 'female' characteristics are varies by culture and society" (see Bell, n.p., for further detail). In this regard, androgyny may pose some problems for data accumulation and analysis in population census by gender.

From the psychological perspective, Kark (2017) describes it³ as an "attributional term used to describe

² Andro- is a latin prefix referring to maleness or men, while -gyn is a root that can be used as either a suffix or prefix meaning woman.

³ Psychological androgyny is first coined by the American psychologist, Sandra Ruth Lipsitz Bem (b.1944-d.2014), and it refers to the idea that an individual could have both masculine and feminine qualities.

an individual who possesses similar (high) levels of stereotypical 'feminine' and 'masculine' psychological attributes or characteristics" (p. 1).

Interest in androgyny has led to several earlier studies mainly with adult subjects (e.g., Constantinople, 1973, Heilbrun & Pitman, 1979; Heilbrun & Schwartz, 1982) and hardly at all with child subjects (Zuker & Torkos, 1989) in the 1970s and 1980s advocating the usefulness of the psycho-social construct with its "implications of a dual sex-role development ... for males and females" and also the removal of "the constraints imposed by stereotypic sex-role conformity" (Heilbrun & Schwartz, 1982, p. 201).

Sexual Awareness in Young Children

Sexual awareness in young children constitutes a part of their sexual development and sexual play, and this is a natural and healthy process that begins during the toddler-hood through early, middle and late childhood into adolescence. According to the National Sexual Violence Resource center (2013), during the infancy phase (ages 0-2 years), toddlers are curious about their body including genitals, touch their private parts in public or private without feeling embarrassed and show no inhibitions around nudity. During the following developmental phase of early childhood (ages 2-5 years), young children may occasionally masturbate, engage in consensual and playful exploration of their body with peers of the same age, may ask questions about sexuality or reproduction, may show curiosity in regard to adult bodies (e.g., touching the mother's breast when bathing together) but continue to show a lack of inhibition around nudity (e.g., taking off their diaper or clothes and walk about naked). This unabashed nudity exists within the realm of collective unconscious for these young children. It constitutes the archetype of Adam and Eve's nakedness and innocence on two different sides of the same coin without an explicit suggestion of androgyny.

The word 'naked' (or 'nakedness') can be explained further by the innocence of Adam and Eve, their being unashamed. Adam and Eve were unclothed and they were not embarrassed. However, the moment they lost their innocence, shame set in, and the couple became ashamed, guilty, as revealed in the use of the word 'naked' as mentioned in the biblical book of Genesis. The first use of the word 'naked' means just that, i.e., 'unclothed' (Genesis 2:25). However, in the second term of 'naked' or

'nakedness' in Genesis 3:7, the Hebrew word *erom* is used differently in form and meaning as distinguished by its use in another biblical book of Deuteronomy 28:48. Its meaning is now more than just the denotative meaning of 'unclothed.' The second word of 'nakedness' carries the connotative idea of being guilty, now exposed and vulnerable to God's judgment, in the aftermath of their disobedience to God. It is not within the scope of this paper to discuss further on this topic, but interested readers can refer to the sermon available on the website of Redeemer Bible Church (2020) as listed in the References.

As how young children perceive the issue of androgyny, the authors postulate that they develop their own schema to categorize or group things they see around them based on what they perceive as being same or similar. For example, a toddler might call all four-legged animals cats or dogs, or s/he might call all men daddies and women mommies (regardless of whether these adults are married and/or have children). This is primordial stereotyping which the authors believe is some form of collective unconscious. As children grow older and/or mature, they learn that their schemata need to be refined to sustain some form of constancy. They try to do this through pondering or by questioning themselves. Many four-year-old children often assume that so long as a person has long hair, s/he is female, until they see a boy/man with long hair (or tied a pony tail) for example. Through pondering or by questioning themselves of what they see around them, they are incessantly trying to refine their mental definition of a particular schema, in this case, what differentiates men from women, boys from girls. This is the emergence of conscious stereotyping of sex or gender with socio-cultural influence and expectations.

The Cephalopod as an Archetype of Adam and Eve

In the similar way that nudity or nakedness is an unabashed experience embedded within the collective unconscious of young children as explained above through the archetype of Adam and Eve's nakedness and innocence, the androgynous cephalopod drawings done by these children also constitutes another phenomenon within their collective unconscious. This is iconographic androgyny (based on the genderless cephalopod drawings) which is certainly different from sociological androgyny and psychological androgyny described earlier above.

According to Callender (n.p.), "Adam was androgynous" (para. 4), and this argument provides a fourth perspective, that of theological androgyny. The name *Adam* comes from the Hebrew word *adama*, which means 'earth' or 'soil.' There is also a variety of

spellings for Adam: Adao, Adan and Adem. In fact, this idea of androgynous Adam is not totally new and can be found in Plato's *Symposium 189c-193e* (see Carnes, 1998, for detail) and had also been discussed in rabbinic circles (Genesis Rabba⁴ 8:1). Adam is conventionally thought of simply as the male half of the first human couple with the other female half being known as Eve (see Figure 3 below for the engraving of Adam and Eve done by the German painter, Albrecht Dürer (b.1471-d.1528), in 1504).

Figure 3. Engraving of Adam and Eve (Albrecht Dürer, 1504)

However, when the definite article *the* precedes the name *Adam* (see Genesis 1:26), the Septuagint⁵ refers to *ho Adam*, i.e., *the Adam*, in addition to *anthropos* or *human*. That is to say, within the literary framework of Genesis 1-5, Callender (n.p.) explained that "the two members of the couple (Adam and Eve) as representing aspects of the single archetypal *adam* - composed of earth (Hebrew, *adamah*; Genesis 2:7) in terms of (i) constituting both male and female potentialities (Genesis 2:21-23; also compare Genesis 1:26-27 and 5:1-2); (ii) being endowed like God with certain capacities (Genesis 2:19-20, 4:1 & 4:25; compare Genesis 1:26-27); and (iii) fatefully acquired wisdom (Genesis 3:6) and becoming like God, knowing good and evil (Genesis 3:22). Hence, the archetypal Adam as well as Eve, being the first human - not 'the man' but rather 'the human' (Meyers, n.p.) - has become a gender-inclusive term. As a result, Callender (n.p.; see also Kessler, 2020, for further detail) argued that the

⁴ *Genesis Rabba* (Hebrew: בְּרֵאשִׁית רַבָּא *B'reshith Rabba*) is a religious text from Judaism's classical period (dated between 300 and 500 CE) with some later additions. "It is a midrash comprising a collection of ancient rabbinical homiletical interpretations of the Book of Genesis (*B'reshith* in Hebrew)" (Wikipedia Contributors, 2022, para. 1).

⁵ The Septuagint (also known as the Greek Old Testament) is the earliest extant Greek translation of books from the Hebrew Bible.

archetypal human (Adam-Eve being androgynous) is “a complex expression of the relational potentialities of class, plurality, and individuality” (para. 1).

Interestingly, Walton (2015) also argued that Adam and Eve are archetypes. This means Adam as well as Eve was “a representative of a group in whom all others in the group are embodied” (Walton, 2015, p. 240). Wu (2015) explained that “[A] person is an archetype if what is true of the one is also true for all those who are represented by in him. Adam and Eve are *historical*, not fictitious. In some sense, Christ, Abraham, and Melchizedek are also archetypes” (para. 8). Hence, according to Wu (2015), Adam and Eve are ancient archetypes and when the two are brought together, they become a theogonic pair - the male-female complementarity that can also be found in the myths and legends of the ancient Middle East, such as Enki and Ninmah or Ninhursaga (Sumerian version), and Tiamat and Apsu (in the Babylonian epic known as *Enuma Elish*), and others in the Far East, such as Izanagi and Izanami (see Davis, 1992, for detail) whose creation is similar to that of Adam and Eve in the Japanese mythology. However, in the Chinese mythology, Nuwa and Fuxi (see Yuan, 2020, for detail), who commonly appear in classic Chinese painting or carving, are not equivalent to Adam and Eve. According to Yuan (2020), the Chinese people were created by goddess Nuwa with yellow clay, while Fuxi was the creator of Chinese culture, which includes scripts, agriculture and the original Eight Trigrams (Yuan, 2020).

Depending on how one chooses to interpret the first androgynous couple of humankind, it is without doubt that the cephalopod drawings produced by young children bear the collective unconscious of the archetype of our primordial parentage. The second author of this paper has also noticed that SHFDs done by demented elderly also resemble the androgynous cephalopods done by young children, as in one of his recent cases (see Figure 4 below).

Figure 4. A Cephalopod Drawing by a demented Elderly

Conclusion

To understand the androgynous state of cephalopod drawings done by young children, it is important to take note that young drawers produce their SHFDs based on what they know or remember than what they see. In other words, these cephalopods or tadpole-like human figures are often agender or genderless, and young drawers are often not conscious of the differences between male and female human figures, making their cephalopods very much hermaphroditic.

Interestingly, this paper has taken into consideration of the four perspectives - sociological, psychological, iconographic and theological (archetypal) - in an attempt to make a brief examination of androgyny observed in cephalopod drawings produced by young children. The authors believe that the SHFDs of young children constitute the primordial stereotyping of genderless human figures (or androgynous archetype) found floating (figuratively) in the deep ocean of their collective unconscious. This could also be the same mental state when demented elderly are asked to draw single human figures as they regress to their primeval cephalopod scribbling.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to acknowledge that the following Figures 1a and 1b are taken from the following source: Singh, M. (2014, August 20). What kids' drawings say about their future thinking skills. Retrieved online [November 9, 2022] from: <https://www.npr.org/sections/health-shots/2014/08/20/341604160/what-kids-drawings-say-about-their-future-thinking-skills/>.

Figures 1c and 1d are taken from the following source: McAteer, O. (2014, August 19). Parents: The quality of your child's drawings is linked to their intelligence ten years later. Retrieved online [November 9, 2022] from: <https://metro.co.uk/2014/08/19/parents-the-quality-of-your-childs-drawings-is-linked-to-their-intelligence-ten-years-later-4837555/>.

Figure 3 is taken from the following source:

The Metropolitan Museum of Art (2000). Adam and Eve 1504 (by Albrecht Dürer). Retrieved online [7 November, 2022] from: <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/336222>

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